

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: NORWAY

Linking Forest to Fish: A Story of Coastal Darkening

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A prominent trend that has received much attention over the past couple of decades is the phenomenon of freshwater “browning”, or “brownification”, notably in northern lakes and rivers (Creed *et al.*, 2018). The proximate cause of this browning is increased concentrations of highly coloured dissolved organic matter (CDOM) made up of large, complex molecules known as humic acids. These molecules, in turn, originate either directly by leachate from vegetation litterfall or roots with associated mycorrhiza, or indirectly via soils and bogs (Fig. 1). The ultimate drivers are more disputed, yet there is evidence that the main causes are reduced acidification

Fig. 1 Natural dissolved organic carbon in a waterfall draining a boreal forest catchment. Photo by DO Hessen.

(Monteith *et al.*, 2007), changes in land use (Finstad *et al.* 2016; Kritzberg *et al.*, 2020) and changes in climate and hydrology (de Wit *et al.*, 2016). The consequences of this browning are first and foremost increased light attenuation, reducing the depth of photosynthesis (Karlsson *et al.*, 2007; Thrane *et al.*, 2014). Secondly these organic molecules, although quite recalcitrant, also form a substratum for heterotrophic bacteria. Together, these changes drive aquatic systems towards net heterotrophy with less uptake of O₂ and increased emissions of CO₂. In a global climate change perspective this is suggested to have a considerable impact, since

Fig. 2 Glacial erosion and permafrost thaw promote coastal darkening in the high Arctic and are major conduits of CO₂ and CH₄ originating from terrestrially fixed carbon.

northern freshwaters are major conduits of terrestrially fixed carbon to the atmosphere (Tranvik *et al.*, 2009). On top of this, browning also reduces the habitat for visual predators (Aksnes & Utne, 1997), promotes deep water anoxia and increase greenhouse gas emissions.

The impacts of freshwater browning in lakes and streams are manifold, but the journey of the humic acids have just begun. Sooner or later this brown freshwater reaches the coast and mixes with saline coastal waters. Even though bacteria and sunlight have had ample time to oxidize and dismantle these complex humic molecules on their way to the coast, a significant portion remains intact (Fransner *et al.*, 2016). The question is then the fate of this recalcitrant DOM in marine systems; is it flocculated and sinks into the sediments, is it diluted to nearly homeopathic and insignificant concentrations, or may it also pose relevant impacts on marine recipient waters?

Before we add the next link to this chain of events, it is worth mentioning that there are other causal routes that move terrestrial carbon into coastal waters. At high latitudes, progressing permafrost thaw and glacier melt promote fluxes of dissolved and particulate matter of terrestrial origin to coastal areas (Fig. 2). Such fluxes are likely an important driver for the pronounced increase in light attenuation that have been recorded for Svalbard fjords in the high Arctic as revealed by remote sensing over the last 30 years (Konik *et al.*, 2021). Also at lower latitudes, increased export of DOM from land has been associated with reduced coastal water clarity (Martin *et al.*, 2021). Indeed, the phenomenon of gradually increasing coastal water light attenuation due to freshwater influence is so commonly observed, it has been termed “coastal water darkening” (Aksnes *et al.*, 2009).

Returning to the drivers, forest planting and afforestation, notably of coniferous forests, are known to promote carbon export and thus browner and darker freshwaters (Finstad *et al.*, 2016; Kritzberg *et al.*, 2020). The link from increased forest volume to darker waters can be attributed to increased net terrestrial net primary production (NPP), and thus an increased export of dissolved organic matter to surface waters. Also, forest planting on former peatlands promotes export of terrestrial DOM (Williamson *et al.*, 2021). Increased concentrations of iron (Fe), typically accompanying organic carbon, also add to this freshwater browning effect. Fe has strong chromophoric properties in itself with a strong absorption towards lower wavelengths and adds to the light attenuation caused by organic carbon.

Although each link in this chain is well understood, few, if any, studies have tried to run the entire length of the chain, from forest to coastal ecosystems. In a recent project, we explored how increased forest cover, representing increased terrestrial net primary production, can influence distant coastal marine ecosystems. To do this, we used a combination of centennial records of forest and coastal water clarity, contemporary optical measurements in lakes and coastal waters, as well as numerical ocean modelling. This approach quite clearly demonstrated a connection from the growing European forests to decreasing coastal water clarity in the Baltic, Kattegat and Skagerrak Seas, and further, how this brown coloured freshwater

Fig. 3 Predicted phytoplankton response to coastal water darkening (Opal *et al.*, 2019). This implies a reduction of the euphotic zone, leading to a delayed, intensified, and prolonged spring bloom. While climate warming is suggested to advance the spring bloom due to earlier shoaling of the mixed layer, it also causes browning in lakes and rivers due to increases in terrestrial greening, ultimately reducing water clarity in downstream coastal areas. These contrasting responses highlight the importance of including water transparency in analyses of phytoplankton phenology and primary production in coastal waters.

can be traced across thousands of kilometres along the Norwegian coast where it determines coastal water clarity causing a two week delay of the phytoplankton spring bloom (Fig. 3; Opdal *et al.*, 2023; Opdal *et al.*, 2019).

Interestingly, while climate warming is generally expected to advance the spring bloom due to earlier shoaling of the mixed layer, it also causes browning in lakes and rivers due to increases in terrestrial greening, ultimately reducing water clarity in downstream coastal areas, effectively causing the spring bloom to occur several weeks later (Fig 3; Opdal *et al.*, 2019). In turn, this will likely also influence the timing of copepod reproduction, whose eggs and nauplii larvae are important food for the early life stages of fish, which might well partly explain the delay in cod spawning already observed between 1929 and 1982 in Lofoten, Norway (Pedersen, 1984) and continuing (Opdal *et al.* unpublished data).

Coastal water darkening also poses a range of other ecosystem impacts. Reduced transparency will favour non-visual feeders (*e.g.* jellyfish) at the expense of fish (Eiane *et al.*, 1999), it will likely also affect autotroph communities and also shift systems towards a larger degree of heterotrophy since increased DOC, yet recalcitrant, could serve as a substratum for heterotrophic bacteria while at the same time reduce photosynthetic activity.

As the project continues, we will continue to explore and disentangle these latter links on phytoplankton, copepods and fish spawning with updated data and timeseries. Nonetheless, the findings so far certainly suggest a striking example on ecosystem connectivity from the boreal forest to the Arctic oceans.

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